

The Mental Health Services among the Persons Deprived of Liberty at Santiago City, District Jail (PDL), A Case Study

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Abstract:- Mental health has emerged as an important public health and concern affected by mental disorders. This study is an in-depth analysis on the Mental Health Services among Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDL) applying Qualitative thematic analysis with the use of a case study design. It concluded that the District Jail is still dependent to outside medical institution in determining the mental health conditions of the persons deprived of liberty and no outright available Psychiatric health Doctor. The health officer of the jail is task only to conduct prime investigation about the background history of the suspected PDL who is suffering from mental illness. Based on the results of the study, we can conclude that the persons deprived of liberty needs to receive a sensible and suitable health care and likewise to establish a distinct and decent hospital for PDL. Through this government project the authorities of the Correction pillar and the PDL would be eased from destitution during court processes due to a lengthy legalistic step in acquiring medical attendance outside the prison cell.

Keywords:- Mental Health Services, Health Officer, Psychiatric Health Doctor, Person Deprived of Liberty.

I. INTRODUCTION

Mental illness is a global problem more than 300 million people suffer from depression, which is about 4.4% of the world's population. These alarming figures reflect the widespread prevalence of mental illness. Mental health conditions affect one in four people at some point in their lives. There are a lot of disparities between countries and different groups of people. The fact that 35-50% of people with severe mental health disorders in the Global North do not receive any treatment is scandalous, but it rises to 76-85% for people living in the South.

There is a wide disparity in the levels of civil society mobilization, which is a key part of any effective response. Mental health organizations representing people with mental health problems and psychosocial disabilities are more prevalent in countries with higher incomes. Women and people who are poor are more likely to be affected by certain issues across the globe. Refugees and asylum seekers are five times more likely to experience mental health issues than the general population. More than 61% of refugees will experience a mental health crisis or breakdown. Mental health is influenced by a variety of factors, similar to how physical health is. These factors can include social and

economic disadvantage and deprivation, low levels of education, unemployment or insecure employment, and discrimination and violence. Sorsha Roberts (2018)

In the Mental Health Law of the Philippines otherwise known as the "Mental Health Act," defined under REPUBLIC ACT No. 11036, which established a National Mental Health Policy for the Purpose of Enhancing the Delivery of Integrated Mental Health Services, Promoting and Protecting the Rights of Persons Utilizing Psychosocial Health Services, Appropriating Funds Therefor and Other Purposes. Under this policy the state affirms the basic right of all Filipinos to mental health as well as the fundamental rights of people who require mental health services. The state commits itself to promoting the well-being of people by ensuring that; mental health is valued, promoted and protected; mental health conditions are treated and prevented; timely, affordable, high quality, and culturally-appropriate mental health care is made available to the public; mental health service are free from coercion and accountable to the service users; and persons affected by mental health conditions are able to exercise the full range of human rights, and participate fully in society and at work free from stigmatization and discrimination.

Meanwhile, numerous reports have also documented the overrepresentation of persons with mental illness in the criminal justice system. Recent estimates suggest that the prevalence of serious mental illness ranges approximately 5%–7% in the community, 6%–12% in jails and 16%–24% in prisons. State prisons, however, have received much less research attention than jails have. There are three to five times as many persons with mental illness in prisons than in mental hospitals, and the number of prison inmates with mental illness continues to increase. Mindy S. Bradley *Et. AL.*, (2010)

Additionally, according to global estimates, about 2.4 million Ghanaians are suffering from some form of mental distress. Despite the fact that relatively little community treatment is available (only 18 psychiatrists are known to be actively practicing in Ghana) and that mental disorders are more prevalent in the community prisoners, there are no known studies of mental disorders in Ghanaian prisons, and there are no forensic psychiatric services available to those who suffer from them. This study aimed to determine how often prisoners in Ghana experience mental distress. global estimates of the prevalence of mental disorders suggests that about 2.4 million Ghanaians have some form of psychiatric distress. Despite the facts that relatively little community-

based treatment is available (only 18 psychiatrists are known to actively practice in Ghana), and that mental disorders are more concentrated among the incarcerated, there is no known research on mental disorders in Ghana prisons, and no forensic mental health services available to those who suffer from them. This study sought to determine the rate of mental distress among prisoners in Ghana. Abdallah Ibrahim *Et. Al.*, (2015)

Along with, many lives in the prison seemed to suffer Mental illnesses, by mere seeing them physically may not reveal the truth in their individual being because this kind of sickness shall undergo extensive medical cognitive processes. Hence, this study aims to determine the Persons Deprived of Liberty if they enjoy their medical health services at Santiago City, District Jail particularly in their mental health concern.

II. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This study aims to determine the Mental Health Services among the Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDL) at Santiago City, District Jail, A case study. Specifically, sought to answer the following;

- What are the medical health services given among the Persons Deprived of Liberty at Santiago City, District Jail?
- What are the health intervention programs given by the Santiago City, District Jail among the Persons Deprived of Liberty?

III. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

For better appreciation of the relationship among the variables in the study, the Theoretical framework is presented using sequential exploratory design in the conduct of the study.

The use of mental health treatments cannot be the only approach to solving mental health problems. “One size fit all” To approach someone is to approach them with the intention of talking to them. We tailor treatment to address individual needs and symptoms. We believe that both remission of psychiatric symptoms and an increase in quality of life are essential for our clients. Our community-based program is specifically tailored to help people with Functional Recovery, Social Recovery, and Mind + Body Wellness. Our philosophy stresses an environment that is free of stigma, judgment, and shame, in order to help people heal. There is a way to approach this problem. We customize treatment to meet the individual needs and symptoms. We have a basic belief that in addition to remission of psychiatric symptoms, we need to improve the quality of life of our clients. Our community-based program is specifically designed to help people who are recovering from functional problems, social issues, and physical wellness. Most importantly, our philosophy prioritizes a healing environment free from stigma, judgment and shame. (<https://themhcollective.com/philosophy>)

According to Freudians’ Theory, the human mind is structured into two main parts: the conscious and unconscious mind. The conscious mind includes all the things we are aware of or can easily bring into awareness.

The unconscious mind, on the other hand, includes all of the things outside of our awareness, all of the wishes, desires, hopes, urges, and memories that lie outside of awareness yet continue to influence behavior. Kendra Cherry (2022)

There are serious gaps and inconsistencies in the delivery of mental health services in the Philippines. The Mental Health Act provides a platform for the delivery of comprehensive and integrated mental health services. Despite advances in the provision of accessible and affordable mental healthcare, there are still many challenges to be overcome. John Lally *Et. Al.*, (2019)

It is worthy also to consider that the first mental health act legislation in Philippine history has been officially signed into law and took effect as the Republic Act No. On June 21, 2018, 11036 was observed. It provides a rights-based mental health law and a comprehensive framework for implementing optimal mental health care in the Philippines. Review the principles and regulations of the 2017 Mental Health Act and their impact on mental health care in the Philippines.

Meanwhile, be it noted that insane people have limited ability to act or are not legally competent to some extent. A Filipino court demands a complete deprivation of intelligence and is declared crazy. However, recent academic research on this subject and progress in international law and other jurisdictions do not support this definition. Filipino law Mental illness, in particular, affects the rights and responsibilities arising from criminal law, inheritance law, and worker accident compensation insurance, so insane reforms are needed as we need to be aware that they occur to a different extent. There must be a policy aimed at removing the stigma associated with mental illness. Assessment of a person's mental state in court proceedings must be interdisciplinary. The *parens patriae* approach and remedies for involuntary treatment need to be reconsidered in the light of a more rights-based approach. Ruby Rossele L. Tugade (2017)

The Prisoners have a high incidence of mental illness, and the transition from prison to the community is a difficult time to provide mental health services, with many negative consequences confirmed during this time. The impact of programs on return to prison should be evaluated further to establish the effect of interventions on clinical outcomes and to clarify the role of interventions on reincarceration. G. Hopkin, *Et. Al* (2018).

Additionally, according to Fazel and Seewald (2012), It is well known that prisoners have a higher incidence of mental health problems than the general public. In-Prison Mental Health Services are increasingly being developed to identify and treat individuals who have been diagnosed with mental health problems in prison. However, the transition from prison to community is stressful for prisoners and their families with mental health problems, and many negative effects have been identified during this time. Maintaining continuity of care between prisons and community health services is difficult, and prisoners often

lose contact with services after being released in which remained to be a problem.

Thus, to consider the Corrections in the life of PDL, this Is one of the essentials of criminal justice administration, and even a pillar. It is tasked with maintaining and rehabilitating those convicted by the Court (PDL). The better part of the person who has been sentenced, the longer period, is in the correction rather than spending the judgment prescribed by the court. Therefore, prison administration is obliged not only to supervise prison officers like prison maintenance, but also to manage their personnel through the need for social concerns. Correction is not limited to areas where prisoners (PDL) are controlled under disciplinary action. Nor is it a reason to control those who violate the law. It is time for so-called law violators and delinquents to resolve social violations in society. Calming down doesn't mean that you should lock them in for the court-mandated idle time to kill time, waste your bike, or waste it. We should concentrate on meeting the demands of social progress, if not perfect. (philippineprisons.wordpress.com/2011/08/09/corrections-in-the-philippines)

In the Correction through the Warden will manage the entire programs of the fourth pillar of the Criminal Justice

System, not only centering for the reformation and rehabilitation of the PDL but also to include the health conditions of the PDL. The Prison/Jail officer while guarding the PDL will also observe their physical being not only in terms of harms from possible attack coming from fellow prisoners and perhaps possible hostile personalities but along with problems on suffering of illnesses such as physical sickness and mental conditions. Observed unusual behavior of a certain PDL by the guard and through possible reports coming from their fellow PDL should be reported immediately to the Prison/Jail Health officer. Health officer will evaluate the condition of the PDL for immediate recommendation of hospitalization to outside clinic or hospital. Expert physicians should unquestionably attend the PDL who will undergo treatment. Diagnostic result of the attending physician will be presented in the court for the judge legal basis in addressing the medical health situation of the PDL for allowing him to undergo treatment outside the prison cell or not.

To further understand the discussion cited above, below are the paradigm of the study on The Mental Health Services among the Persons Deprived of Liberty at Santiago City, District Jail (PDL).

As shown Below, figure 1. Paradigm of the study;

Fig. 1: Paradigm of the Study

IV. DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design and Methodology

A qualitative research approach particularly a Case Study design was used to this study. A case study is an in-depth study of a particular research problem rather than a sweeping statistical survey or comprehensive comparative inquiry. It is often used to narrow down a very broad field of research into one or a few easily researchable examples. The case study research design is also useful for testing whether a specific theory and model actually applies to phenomena in the real world. It is a useful design when not much is known about an issue or phenomenon. De Vaus, (2006).

B. Population and Locale of the Study

The population of this study was focused on the Five (5) Persons Deprive with Liberty and two (2) Jail Personnel of the District Jail of Santiago City Isabela in order to determine the medical health services given among the PDL. Each of the respondent were agreed on the interview and signed a consent form prior to participating, the researcher also promised and ensured that their identity will be kept confidential.

C. Data Gathering Instrument

The data were gathered using an In-Depth Interview. The term “in-depth” is defined fairly vague in the literature: it generally means a one-to-one interview on one general topic, which is covered in detail. Usually, these qualitative interviews last about an hour, although sometimes much longer. It sounds like two people having a discussion, but there are differences in the power dynamics, and end goal: for the classic sociologist Burgess (2002) these are “conversations with a purpose”.

D. Data Gathering Procedure

Immediately after approval of this research proposal, the researcher conducted data gathering by means of in-depth interview. Often, with only an occasional question from the researcher for clarification, the participants talked about a wide variety of topics throughout an extended interview. All interviews were recorded. The interviews were informal and open-ended, and carried out in a conversational style.

The researcher wrote field notes in conjunction with the interviews, follow-up interviews, observations, and casual encounters with subjects. Notes were also being written while listening to recorded interviews, typing transcripts, and reflecting upon a particular interview. In addition to the interviews and follow-up interviews, the researcher will obtain other data throughout the study, such as comments from administrative and teaching colleagues, papers or other materials and on-going literature review.

E. Ethical Consideration

This study is guided by the ethical principles on research. The research ethics was focused on requirements of voluntary participation, informed consent, confidentiality and the personal safety of the participants and the researcher.

The participants of this study are not force nor coerce to participate in this study. They can decline to answer the

question for any reason. They can also withdraw their participation in this research verbally and/or return the unfinished questionnaire to the researcher. Debriefing will also be conducted to stabilize the psychological condition of the participants. Moreover, strict confidentiality and anonymity of the participants are always observing and maintain. Lastly, no money was given to the participants however, token of appreciation was considered.

F. Treatment of Data

To treat the qualitative data, a thematic analysis by Creswell (2018) was utilized by the researcher. Thematic analysis is a method of analyzing qualitative data. It is usually applied to a set of texts; such as interview transcripts. The researcher closely examined the data to identify common themes – topics, ideas and patterns of meaning that come up repeatedly.

V. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents, analyzes, and interprets the findings of the study on the Mental Health Services among the Persons Deprived of Liberty at Santiago City, District Jail (PDL).

A. Part 1. The medical health services given among the PDL.

a) Health assessment Condition

In the verbatim responses of the participants, the health officer of Santiago City District Jail said that, “they asses health condition of the PDL thru Blood Pressure (BP) and Temperature monitoring in relation to Covid 19 Pandemic”. The jail officer has then told that they conduct, “vital signs monitoring and initial assessment” to PDL. The PDL also answered that, “*Ang pagbibigaynila ng gamotayonsanararamdamannamin. Check nila ang blood pressure, body temperature. Pinupuntahannila ang bawatselda o mgakapatidsaloob para tanungin ang sitwasyonnamin at ano ang mganararamdamsaamingmgararili*”. (They prescribe and gave us medicine, checked our blood pressures and body temperatures. They visit our cells and fellow prisoners in order to determine our situations and conditions inside the Jail). The result of interview conducted to the participants revealed that there are medical health services given among the Person Deprived of Liberty: The Jail Health Officer of the District Jail of Santiago City and with the assistance of the Jail Officer on duty religiously conduct various medical health services like the accompanying and escorting the Person Deprived of Liberty in going to hospitals, assess health conditions through checking regularly on vital signs, blood pressure and temperature monitoring particularly in relation to COVID 19 pandemic, administering the proper medicines on headaches, stomachaches, toothaches, skin allergies, primary trauma, mental and emotional stress, sleep deprivation and sexually transmitted diseases.

Kuosmanen, *Et.*, *Al* (2009) Deprivation of liberty (DL) in inpatient care is common worldwide. As liberty is a central element of patients' rights, there is a need to develop most effective methods supporting patients' personal liberty. This is also true with the practice of the district of Santiago City Jail when they assess the health condition of those deprived of liberty. The UK Supreme Court's judgment in "*Cheshire West and Chester Council v P [2014]*" fundamentally changed the approach to determining if a person who lacked capacity was deprived of their liberty by the State. (Richard Griffith, 2015)

b) Health Education Program

Despite of the nifty management of the personnel inside this district Jail. The condition of the PDL inside the Jail Facility is considered uncondusive due to obvious poor conditions brought by overcrowding and incidental unsanitary circumstances due to limited rooms, hygiene supplies and facility resources to make the institution well maintained. That in order to sustain and manage their health conditions the District Jail under their medical services conducts Regular Health Education Program: *The Jail health officer said that they are: "conducting regular health education," The Jail officer acclaimed that they are having regular sunning and zumba exercises and other physical activities to promote wellness (indoor and outdoor sports), and the PDL participants responded that, "mgakaragdangang medical supply gamot at gamit pang emergency upanglaginghanda ang health section at magkaroon ng training at seminars ang mga PDL upangmaginghanda din silasaanumangsakuna o emergency at magingkatulungan din ng serbisyo medical".* (There is a need for additional medical supplies, medicines, and emergency kits for the continual readiness of the health section of the Jail. Trainings and seminars on crisis and emergency management should be conducted and participated by the PDL for them to become ready all the time, the PDL can also serve and extend help on medical services inside the District Jail). The Zumba exercises, leading sunning and other physical activities to promote wellness, indoor and outdoor sports, implementation on minimum health protocols for newly committed PDL, regular conduct of Acid Fat Bacillus (AFB) Smearing and Staining to prevent prevalence of Pulmonary Tuberculosis (PTB), and assisting them in Human Immune Deficiency Syndrome (HIV) Screening. All these medical services are implemented conscientiously by the authorities concern at the district Jail of Santiago City spearheaded through the Jail Health Officer and with the help of their staff personnel and summoned Jail Officers on duty during their scheduled medical services and activities.

Meredith Nelson et.al (2006) in their research, the moderate physical activity provides substantial health benefits for individuals not only in fitness,

athletic, and health organizations, but also for individuals who struggle with addictions and behaviors in correctional programs. The study conducted in maximum security correctional facility is to examine the relationship between physical activity and offender attitudes. It shows also that regular moderate physical activity produces positive mental and physical benefits for offenders. Moreover, the research suggests that such educational programs can provide positive steps toward productive, healthy, and anti-criminal lifestyles.

c) Medical Check-up and Attendance

The jail health officer answered that, "*yes by means of submitting health assessment of PDL to their respective lawyers prior to motion for medical check-up and in emergency referral in extreme cases*". The PDL 1 in his response said that, "*opo ang district jail ay nagbibigay ng gamot. Sila po ay inaasikasokamingganasalooob at ginagamot o kaya ipinapagamot.*" The PDL 2 acclaimed also that, "*agad naman inaakasyonanginagamot o binibigyanlunas ang mgapumupuntasa health section upangmagpakunsulta.*" (*Yes certainly, the district jail gave us our needed medicines, they took care of us prisoners inside the Jail, they are treating us and sending us for hospitalization. The PDL 2 also acclaimed that, we were responded immediately, first aid and treatment were given to PDL to all of those who go at the health section seeking for a medical consultation.*)

In consideration to the possible jeopardy factors of following administrative procedures especially in the part of personnel of Santiago district jail management, the PDL who are suspected sick are not just allowed automatically to be sent in the hospital either public or private, instead they will have their self-medications first but are thoroughly monitored by the health officer. The Medical Health Unit of the jail through the health Officer will assess the PDL who are indeed observed sick. If the PDL suffers extreme cases of sickness upon positive result of their medical assessment, the "health assessment result" will be proximately submitted to their respective lawyers to be utilized as their legal basis for filing a motion in the court to undergo medical check-up. At this point, within the senses of the honorable court through the attending judge, the PDL who have severe cases of sickness should be permitted or temporarily release from the prison cell and are therefore endorsed to be committed immediately in the public or private medical institutions for their appropriate hospitalization upon due referral and recommendation of a competent medical physician.

The improvements in community health care quality through error reduction have been slow to transfer to correctional settings. The researchers convened a panel of correctional experts, which

recommended 60 patients safety standards focusing on such issues as creating safety cultures at organizational, supervisory, and staff levels through changes to policy and training and by ensuring staff competency, reducing medication errors, encouraging the logical transfer of information between and within practice settings, and developing mechanisms to detect errors or near misses and to shift the emphasis from blaming staff to fixing systems. To their knowledge, this is the first published set of standards focusing on patient safety in prisons, adapted from the emerging literature on quality improvement in the community. Marc F. Stern MD, MPH,*et.al* (2010).

User Voice was commissioned by the National Guideline Centre, Royal College of Physicians (RCP) to carry out research concerning the physical health of prisoners. 45 prisoners were spoken to and five prisons were accessed in order to run focus groups with long term prisoners, short term prisoners, female prisoners, prisoners with experience of substance misuse, older prisoners and prisoners with disabilities. The RCP were interested in gaining an insight into the experiences of these specific groups of prisoners and their involvement in health services in prison, in particular, concerning their physical health needs relating to improving health care services, continuity of care and including post release prescriptions.

B. Part II. The health Intervention programs given by the Santiago City District Jail among the Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDL).

a) Tele consultation Program

According to the health officer he stated that, *“due to our pandemic situation, we initiated the “TELECONSULTATION” as an innovative program to address the medical needs of our PDL”*. The jail officer answered, *“teleconsultation”* and the PDL 2 responded also that, *“ang mgangatanggap ng PDL ay maramitulad ng bakuna:Flu vaccine,sinovac, pneumonia vaccine, BP monitoring at HIV testing upangmalaman ang estado ng amingkalusugan at kung hindi kaya ay meron pang Teleconsultation.”(We the PDL received various medical intervention programs like Flu Vaccine, Sinovac, Pneumonia Vaccine, BP monitoring and HIV testing for us to determine our state of health conditions. Teleconsultation is also real and programmed among us PDL inside the District Jail.)*

The health Intervention programs given by the Santiago City District Jail among the Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDL) is the TELECONSULTATION. Amidst to deadly Covid 19 they initiated this Medical Health Program as an innovative step to address the medical needs of the PDL under the pandemic situation. Further, this resulted to the institution to kept a record of no Covid Cases during the early height of pandemic as their best practices in their institution.

The Persons Denied of Liberty are human beings, regardless maybe that in the actual scenario of their alleged commissions are guilty by actuality of their actions, yet, respecting the propriety of law the PDL are presumed innocent until proven beyond reasonable doubt with their respective charges. They deserved to be treated well inside the prison cell with most of their basic rights except to liberty. At Santiago City District Jail the personnel has religiously observe and respect all the time the rights of the PDL. One manifestation to show the dedication of the jail personnel and the whole management is the explicit and empathetic giving of health care program among said PDL. The district city jail Address the various sickness of the PDL by way of the following medical steps and processes: They conduct initial assessment including vital signs and provisions of appropriate medicine particularly to ordinary sickness like head ache, tooth ache, stomach ache and skin allergies. The first aid application and provision of appropriate nursing intervention and referral to proper health authorities is also applied to PDL who suffers Primary Trauma. The Conducting of therapeutic communication such as individual and group counselling and referral to a health authority if necessary is also undertaken to sickness of PDL like: emotional stress, mental stress and sleep deprivation. Regular health education is also conducted to avoid sexually transmitted diseases among the PDL.

To the Persons Deprived of Liberty suffered with mental illnesses at Santiago City District Jail are being catered by the health officer by commonly talking first to the family of the PDL for a history tracking on the preceding condition purposely to determine the previous management and the possible medicines he had intake in the past days if there are any, after which they will be scheduled for an online consultation or face to face Nuero - Psychiatric Evaluation to a specialist at Cagayan Valley Medical Center (CVMC) under the Department of Behavioral Medicine of the Hospital situated at Tuguegarao City.

While the delivery of healthcare services within prison systems is underpinned by different models, access to timely and optimal healthcare is often constrained by multifaceted factors. Telehealth has been used as an alternative approach to conventional care. To date, much of the focus has been on evaluation of telehealth interventions within certain geographical contexts such as rural and remote communities. Therefore, the aim of this systematic review was to synthesize the evidence base to date for the impacts of, and outcomes from, tele health delivered in prisons. Esther Jie Tian *Et.Al* (2021).

VI. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the conclusion and recommendations of this research.

A. Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it concluded that the Mental Health Services among the Persons Deprived of Liberty at Santiago City, District Jail is still dependent to outside medical institution. The health officer of the jail is tasked only to conduct prime investigation about the background history of the suspected PDL who is suffering from mental illness, later the PDL is referred to a Nuero - Psychiatric Specialist for a virtual or face to face consultation and medical evaluation for purposes of hospital confinement, but provided that the PDL has undergone the legal processes in the court to undergo medical attendance outside the district jail.

B. Recommendations

In the light of the findings and conclusions of the study, the following are recommended:

- The prisoners need to receive a sensible and suitable health care through a self-governing review of health care services inside the prison.
- The jails and prisons need to identify strong point of programs and opportunities for further improvements towards medical services particularly mental maladies.
- For the better reformation and rehabilitation of the PDL, the Philippine government through a certain statute need to establish a distinct hospital for PDL as what the other government agencies has, special attention is essential to PDL with mental illnesses hence they are perilous among other PDL inside the cell.
- Through this government project the authorities of the Correction pillar and the PDL would be eased from destitution during court processes due to a lengthy legalistic step in acquiring medical attendance outside the prison cell.

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